

Volumetric Estimation of Chlorides and Sulphates in a Mixture Containing both, with the Help of an Adsorption Indicator.

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The use of dyestuffs as what Kolthoff calls 'adsorption indicators' in volumetric analysis, is of recent origin. Various methods have been suggested for the estimation of Cl, Br, I, Ag, (Fajans and Hassel, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1923, 29, 495) oxalates (Wellings, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1932, 28, 565), volumetrically with the help of adsorption indicators.

During recent times Wellings (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1932, 28, 561) suggested a method for estimation of sulphates volumetrically using fluorescein as an adsorption indicator. The authors have tested the method and found it quite satisfactory, though it must be admitted that a good deal of practice is needed to enable one to judge the end-point correctly. The scope of Wellings' method is, however, very limited as good results are not obtained in presence of chlorides, nitrate and free acids. In the present paper the authors have found out a method not only of eliminating the interference caused by the presence of chlorides in the estimation of sulphates but they have developed a method of estimating volumetrically both the chloride and the sulphate one after the other in the same solution.

It is also found that the sulphate can be estimated even in the presence of free acid (HCl and acetic), provided the free acid is just neutralised by dilute ammonia, the excess of ammonia being boiled off, before titrating the solution against standard baryta. It has, however, not been found possible to get over the interference caused by nitrates and nitric acid.

Since the authors found by experiments that the presence of free acetate ($\text{CH}_3\text{COO}'$) ions does not interfere in the titration of sulphate by barium hydroxide, a solution of CH_3COOAg is added to a solution containing the chloride and sulphate till all the chloride ions are precipitated. After this the sulphate is easily estimated by Wellings' method. The precipitated AgCl does not in any way interfere.

The next step was to estimate the amount of chloride first by using a standard solution of silver acetate with fluorescein indicator which changes colour from white to brick red. After the estimation of chloride, the same solution containing the precipitated AgCl , is titrated further against standard baryta solution, the indicator fluorescein present in the solution now changing colour from yellow—pink—orange, when the sulphate is completely precipitated. The amount of chloride can be calculated from the volume of the standard silver acetate solution used, while the volume of the baryta required gives the amount of $\text{SO}_4^{=}$ in solution.

Mixtures containing, (1) $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and KCl ; (2) $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and NaCl ; (3) Na_2SO_4 and NaCl ; (4) K_2SO_4 and KCl ; (5) $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ and KCl and (6) $3\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and KCl were estimated by the method given above volumetrically and quantitative results were obtained showing that the sulphates and the chlorides when present together can be estimated volumetrically one after the other.

Mixtures containing the various sulphates acidified with varying but known quantities of HCl were taken. The acid was neutralised by dilute ammonia and Cl^- ion precipitated with silver acetate. The solution on titration with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ gave quantitative results for the $\text{SO}_4^{=}$ present in the solution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

(A) A solution of baryta was prepared and standardised from time to time by $M/10$ -succinic acid, prepared from Merck's analytical reagent.

(B) The following solutions were prepared from pure reagents, the strength in each case was confirmed by the estimation of SO_4 gravimetrically as BaSO_4 and also volumetrically by the method of Wellings.

$M/10\text{-MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	...	24.60 g./litre.
$M/10\text{-Na}_2\text{SO}_4$	...	14.20
$M/10\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4$	...	17.40
$M/10\text{-(NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	...	13.20
$3\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$	...	19.23

(C) The solutions of the following chlorides were prepared from Merck's analytical reagents.

<i>N</i> /20-NaCl	2.925 g. in a litre.
<i>N</i> /20-KCl	3.725 " "

(D) Pure silver acetate was prepared from AgNO_3 first by precipitation of Ag as carbonate and subsequently dissolving in glacial acetic acid and recrystallising. The solution of silver acetate was standardised by standard thiocyanate (Volhard's method and also by standard KCl solution, Mohr's method). The strength of the solution used was 7.5910 g./litre.

(E) Fluorescein indicator : 1 G. of fluorescein was dissolved by boiling it with 50 c.c. of rectified spirit and making up the solution to 100 c.c. with the same solvent. All solutions were prepared in CO_2 free distilled water.

Different sulphates (25c.c. to 50 c.c.) were taken to which varying amounts of different chlorides from 1 c.c. to 30c.c. were added. The mixtures were first titrated against standard silver acetate for the chloride and then against standard baryta for the sulphate. 5 C.c. of 5% solution of magnesium acetate were added in each case, (excepting in the case of magnesium sulphate), before titrating it with baryta solution, because the colour change with fluorescein occurs only on the colloidal particles of magnesium and manganese hydroxide and not on the BaSO_4 (cf. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1932, 23, 563). It was also found that cadmium sulphate solution could also be titrated against Ba(OH)_2 like magnesium and manganese sulphate, *i.e.*, it did not require the addition of any magnesium acetate.

From the numerous experiments that were performed with mixtures containing the sulphates mentioned above and alkali chlorides, it was found that the volume of the silver acetate required for the titration of the chloride in the mixture, was exactly the same as that required for the calculated quantity of the chloride present in the mixture, and the sulphate could be estimated in the mixture within an error of 0.4%.

The results obtained by titration are summarised in the table given below :

Mixture of chloride and sulphate (c.c.).	Ag-acetate.	Ba(OH) ₂ .	Chloride per litre.		Sulphate per litre.	
			Expt.	Theo.	Expt.	Theo.
4.0 KCl + 25.0 MgSO ₄	4.40c.c.	26.10 c.c.	3.725g.	3.725g.	24.69g.	24.60g.
15.0 ,, + 30.0 ,,	16.50	31.30	„	„	„	„
30.0 ,, + 50.0 ,,	33.00	52.20	„	„	„	„
5.0NaCl + 25.0MgSO ₄	5.50	26.10	2.93	2.91	„	„
20.0 ,, + 40.0 ,,	22.00	41.70	„	„	„	„
4.0NaCl + 25.00Na ₂ SO ₄	4.40	26.10	2.93	2.94	14.25	14.20
15.0 ,, + 30.0 ,,	16.50	31.30	„	„	„	„
9.0KCl + 25.0Na ₂ SO ₄	9.90	26.10	3.725	3.725	17.33	17.40
30.0 ,, + 50.0 ,,	39.00	52.20	„	„	„	„
15.0 ,, + 30.0CaSO ₄	16.50	23.40	3.725	3.725	19.22	19.23
20.0 ,, + 40.0 ,,	22.00	29.20	„	„	„	„

SUMMARY.

1. The sulphate in the solution can be volumetrically estimated by a standard solution of baryta even in the presence of a chloride.

2. The chloride and the sulphate in a mixture can be estimated volumetrically one after the other by silver acetate and baryta respectively, fluorescein serving as an adsorption indicator for both.

3. The sulphate can be estimated by baryta by the method suggested in this paper even in the presence of HCl and CH₃COOH provided the acid is neutralised by ammonia before titration.

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